

We studied the effects of hot water treatment (55, 60, and 65 °C for 15, 30, and 45 min) and dry heat treatment (55, 60, and 65 °C for 3, 5, and 7 d) on germination and seed and seedling vigor (total dehydrogenase activity as measured by optical density [OD] of seeds stained with tetrazolium chloride and seedling dry weight after 7 d germination) in IR36, IR64, and Intan Gawri. Tests were made immediately after treatment and after storing treated seeds for 3 mo under ambient conditions (22-25 °C, 65-70% relative humidity).

For the hot water treatment, half the seeds were presoaked for 3 h at 22 °C, half were treated dry. Fungal infection was measured using the blotter method in four replications of 25 seeds each.

Hot water treatment of both dry and presoaked seeds at 55 °C for up to 45 min had no adverse effect on seed germination and vigor before or after storage. In fact, there was a slight improvement in seed vigor (see table). Treated seeds showed considerably lower fungal incidence than control, the difference was more pronounced with presoaked seeds.

At 60 °C, hot water treatment for 15 min had no adverse effect on dry seeds but it was highly deleterious to presoaked seeds. Treatment for 30 or 45 min resulted in marked reduction in germination and vigor, even in dry seeds. The adverse effects were more pronounced after storage.

The most drastic reduction in germination and vigor was in seeds treated with hot water at 65 °C. While dry seeds could partially withstand treatment up to 15 min, in all other cases seeds became nonviable.

Dry heat treatment resulted in considerably lower fungal incidence and did not have any adverse effect on germination and vigor of seeds before or after storage.

Hot water treatment of dry or presoaked seeds for 15-45 min at 55 °C and dry heat treatment at 55-65 °C for up to 7 d can be practiced without adverse effects on seed vigor. □

Effect of hot water and dry heat treatment on germination, seedling vigor, and fungal infection of rice seed.^a IIRRI, 1989.

Treatment	After treatment				After storage ^b	
	Germination (%)	Dehydrogenase activity (OD)	Seedling dry wt (mg)	Fungal infection (%)	Germination (%)	Seedling dry wt (mg)
Hot water						
No presoaking						
55 °C 15 min	97.5 ± 1.58	0.31 ± 0.03	9.98 ± 0.76	38.3 ± 6.7	100.0 ± 0	9.66 ± 1.33
30 min	94.2 ± 3.37	0.34 ± 0.02	9.30 ± 0.97	58.3 ± 2.35	98.3 ± 1.67	9.60 ± 1.53
45 min	97.6 ± 1.20	0.25 ± 0.003	10.10 ± 1.66	53.3 ± 4.41	98.3 ± 1.67	8.80 ± 1.25
60 °C 15 min	96.6 ± 1.66	0.25 ± 0.043	9.45 ± 1.18	55.0 ± 7.64	91.7 ± 2.88	8.16 ± 0.92
30 min	79.6 ± 2.60	0.19 ± 0.01	9.01 ± 1.82	38.3 ± 6.64	80.6 ± 4.26	8.00 ± 1.27
45 min	31.0 ± 13.88	0.19 ± 0.01	8.40 ± 2.2	25.0 ± 5.78	41.0 ± 14.87	5.76 ± 0.63
65 °C 15 min	54.0 ± 15.63	0.19 ± 0.07	8.99 ± 1.07	21.6 ± 11.5	58.3 ± 13.41	8.40 ± 0.87
Presoaked^d						
55 °C 15 min	91.7 ± 6.66	0.22 ± 0.03	10.23 ± 1.39	51.7 ± 9.24	93.3 ± 1.65	8.87 ± 1.48
30 min	98.7 ± 1.33	0.27 ± 0.03	9.60 ± 1.26	51.6 ± 4.41	90.0 ± 4.71	9.30 ± 1.25
45 min	88.0 ± 17.43	0.23 ± 0.05	9.74 ± 1.27	41.7 ± 3.33	93.7 ± 5.17	8.73 ± 1.27
60 °C 15 min	43.7 ± 11.03	0.27 ± 0.017	7.74 ± 1.84	26.7 ± 7.27	21.7 ± 4.28	4.03 ± 0.16
30 min	19.5 ± 6.36	0.26 ± 0.02	5.60 ± 0.24	20.0 ± 7.07	0	-
45 min	13.0 ± 1.36	0.20 ± 0.02	8.99 ± 1.07	17.5 ± 2.04	0	-
Dry heat						
55 °C 3 d	98.3 ± 1.67	0.32 ± 0.03	9.65 ± 0.98	36.7 ± 4.90	93.3 ± 2.72	9.23 ± 0.97
5 d	99.0 ± 1.0	0.29 ± 0.04	9.92 ± 0.29	32.0 ± 3.6	98.3 ± 1.67	9.83 ± 1.57
7 d	98.0 ± 0.9	0.34 ± 0.02	9.55 ± 1.04	40.0 ± 2.36	98.3 ± 1.67	9.66 ± 1.34
60 °C 3 d	99.0 ± 1.0	0.33 ± 0.28	9.23 ± 1.36	48.3 ± 3.33	98.3 ± 1.67	9.70 ± 1.31
5 d	99.0 ± 1.0	0.34 ± 0.02	9.19 ± 1.08	51.7 ± 4.41	98.0 ± 1.63	9.37 ± 1.05
7 d	100.0 ± 0.0	0.34 ± 0.02	9.95 ± 1.30	40.0 ± 4.71	91.0 ± 5.44	8.47 ± 0.95
65 °C 3 d	97.3 ± 1.45	0.32 ± 0.10	3.42 ± 1.81	46.6 ± 6.79	94.7 ± 2.59	10.4 ± 1.94
5 d	99.0 ± 1.0	0.36 ± 0.03	9.36 ± 1.25	46.6 ± 6.79	100.0 ± 0.0	9.07 ± 0.96
7 d	100.0 ± 0.0	0.37 ± 0.02	9.33 ± 1.34	38.3 ± 8.93	98.8 ± 0.97	9.46 ± 1.13
Control	93.6 ± 1.85	0.28 ± 0.05	9.02 ± 1.19	73.3 ± 5.44	99.0 ± 0.82	8.9 ± 1.02

^aMean of three cultivars (each with two replications) ± SEM. ^bThree months under ambient conditions. ^cAt 65 °C germination after treatment was zero with hot water at 30 and 45 min. ^dAt 65 °C, germination after treatment and after storage for 15, 30, and 45 min was zero.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Contribution of different soil Zn fractions to Zn uptake by rice

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Zn in soil occurs in a number of distinct chemical fractions that differ in their solubility, and thus in the availability of the Zn to plants. We studied the contribution of these fractions to Zn uptake by rice in 15 soils of Bangladesh. Two 25-d-old rice seedlings (cv. BR3) were grown for 55 d in each earthen pot containing 2.5 kg air-dried soil and 2 cm standing water.

Zn fractionation data were obtained using the scheme of Murthy, as modi-

Path coefficient analysis showing direct and indirect effects of different fractions of soil Zn on rice plant uptake.

Variable	Water-soluble Zn	Exchangeable Zn	Complexed Zn	Organic Zn	Amorphous sesquioxide Zn	Crystalline sesquioxide Zn	Residual Zn	Correlation with Zn uptake <i>r</i>
Water-soluble Zn	0.0094 ^a	0.0034	-0.0001	0.0009	0.0024	-0.0020	-	-0.1463
Exchangeable Zn	-0.2453	-0.6738 ^a	-0.465	-0.0510	-0.4770	-0.0389	0.1709	-0.0656
Complexed Zn	-0.0146	0.9136	1.3238 ^a	0.5479	0.9396	0.1861	-0.8276	-0.0091
Organic Zn	-0.0556	-0.0425	-0.2323	-0.5612 ^a	-0.1354	0.0423	0.1923	-0.2877
Amorphous sesquioxide Zn	-0.0054	-0.0149	-0.0149	-0.0051	-0.0210 ^a	-0.0038	0.0047	-0.0209
Crystalline sesquioxide Zn	0.1693	-0.0462	-0.1125	0.0603	-0.1463	-0.8000 ^a	-0.3668	-0.2437
Residual Zn	-0.0042	-0.2054	-0.5081	-0.2795	-0.1833	0.3727	0.8129 ^a	-0.0136

^aDirect effects. All other effects are indirect.

fied by Mandal and Mandal. Much of the native Zn (46.2-84.5%) was in the residual mineral fraction. That fraction contributed very little to plant uptake.

The water-soluble, exchangeable, complexed, and organically bound fractions were the most important; content in the different soils ranged from 0.044 to 0.8, 0.073 to 1.2, 1.71 to

16.4, and 1.25 to 26.43% in different soils. Amorphous and crystalline sesquioxide-bound Zn ranged from 2.03 to 8.91 and 1.86 to 5.12%, respectively.

Path coefficient analysis was used to identify the relative contribution of different fractions to Zn uptake by rice. Values were highest for the complexed

Zn (1.324), followed by that for residual Zn (0.813) (see table). The other fractions showed no dominant effect on Zn uptake. The overall negative correlations of all fractions with Zn uptake indicate that native soil Zn fractionation values after incubation with applied Zn would be more useful to predict Zn uptake by rice. □

Crop management

Response of rice to applied P in soils of different P status

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We conducted a 2-yr greenhouse experiment to study the response of rice to fertilizer P on soils of different agroclimatic regions of Punjab. Soils varied in available P (Olsen extractable) from low (1.72 ppm) to high (39.20 ppm) and in texture from loamy sand to silty clay loam.

P was applied as monoammonium phosphate at 0, 6.6, 13.2, 19.8, and 26.4 ppm P to 7 kg soil in polyethylene-lined 10-kg enamel pots. Recommended N, K, and Zn were applied. PR106 raised in sand culture was transplanted 35 d after seeding at 4 hills/pot and 2 plants/hill. Water level was maintained at 2 cm throughout.

Applied P significantly increased yield both years in soils testing low and medium in available P (see table). Rice in soils high in available P did not respond to applied P. Seven of 8 low-P

soils and 3 of 5 medium-P soils responded significantly to fertilizer P the first year; 8 of 9 low-P soils and 6 of 11 medium-P soils responded significantly to P the second year.

P removal by the rice crop ranged from an average 60 mg/pot in low-P soils to 119 mg/pot in high-P soils (see

table). The increase in P uptake with increased applied P was significant up to 19.8 ppm P in low-P soils and 6.6 ppm P in medium-P soils the first year and up to 19.8 ppm P in both low- and medium-P soils the second year. Differences in P uptake in high-P soils were not significant either year. □

Effect of P level on rice yields and P uptake in soils with different levels (0-26.4ppm) of available P. Punjab, India.

Available P	Year	0	6.6 ppm	13.2 ppm	19.8 ppm	26.4 ppm	LSD (0.05)
<i>Rice yield (g/pot)</i>							
Low	1	20.2	25.0	28.4	28.4	28.7	1.5
	2	14.6	28.0	34.6	36.6	-	1.7
	Mean	18.4	26.5	31.5	32.5	-	
Medium	1	26.0	29.4	32.5	31.2	30.0	1.7
	2	30.4	36.2	38.9	39.5	-	1.4
	Mean	29.2	32.8	35.7	35.4	-	
High	1	30.5	30.4	30.8	30.4	30.6	ns
	2	36.9	37.4	36.7	37.7	-	ns
	Mean	33.7	33.7	33.8	34.1	-	
<i>P uptake (mg/pot)</i>							
Low	1	60.0	80.9	76.6	100.8	93.4	5.6
	2	42.3	63.4	83.9	93.5	-	5.6
	Mean	51.2	77.2	79.9	97.1	-	
Medium	1	85.6	95.5	99.8	107.2	111.6	4.8
	2	91.7	106.2	117.3	127.6	-	3.9
	Mean	88.6	98.8	108.8	117.4	-	
High	1	98.3	98.8	102.7	105.3	106.6	7.1
	2	119.0	122.3	124.4	122.6	-	ns
	Mean	108.6	110.5	113.5	114.5	-	